

GREED VS GRIEVANCE THESIS: A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF THE DRIVERS OF BOKO HARAM CONFLICT

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In this paper, I am going to be critically analyzing the drivers of Boko Haram conflicts drawing on the greed vs grievance thesis. I will be arguing that Boko Haram terrorism is pretty much a result of genuine grievances at the initial start as opposed to greed. Although this metamorphosed into greed at the later stage of the conflict, my argument will be supported with relevant references and sources as well as government reports. I will be critically discussing the frustration-aggression, and the relative deprivation theories of grievance thesis to support my argument.

FRUSTRATION AGGRESSION THEORY

In their book "Frustration and Aggression," Dollard et al. (1939) introduced the concept of "frustration-aggression," which posits that individuals may experience negative emotions such as anger, annoyance, and irritation, leading to violent behavior when their goal attainment is impeded by obstacles. This theory has been widely applied to various forms of aggressive behavior, including international conflicts. Berkowitz (1962) expanded on this theory by introducing the concept of "catharsis," which involves the release of pent-up frustration through aggressive behavior. Additionally, Berkowitz argued that the presence of weapons could increase the likelihood of aggression. In the context of armed conflict, frustration resulting from political repression, economic inequality, and social exclusion has been identified as key drivers of violence and aggression (Horgan, 2017). Levy and Thompson (2010) suggest that frustration with current economic, political, or social conditions can be a major factor leading to violent conflicts and wars. Therefore, addressing the underlying causes of frustration, such as economic deprivation, political oppression, and social inequality, may be essential to prevent the emergence of armed conflicts.

Despite its popularity, the frustration-aggression theory has received criticism for oversimplification and lack of consideration for other factors that contribute to aggression, such as personality traits, cultural norms, and situational factors (Bushman et al., 2001). Empirical support for the theory has also been questioned, with recent research suggesting that frustration alone may not be sufficient to trigger aggression (Berkowitz, 1989). Moreover, Gurr (1970, 1993) has argued against the application of the frustration-aggression theory to armed conflicts, claiming that such conflicts are often rooted in deep-seated grievances such as political oppression or economic inequality. Gurr contends that individuals and groups engage in armed conflict when they perceive violence to be the only means of achieving their goals. The frustration-aggression theory, therefore, fails to account for the role of identity and ideology in such conflicts. Armed conflicts are often driven by strong beliefs and values, such as religious or ethnic identity, rather than solely resulting from frustration (Gurr, 2000). Alternative theories, such as the appraisal theory, have been proposed to explain aggression. The appraisal theory suggests that how individuals interpret a frustrating situation determines whether or not aggression will occur (Marcus-Newhall et al., 2000).

RELATIVE DEPRIVATION THEORY

Gurr (1970) introduced the relative deprivation theory as a supplement to Dollard et al.'s frustration-aggression theory. The theory posits that grievances arise when there is a discrepancy between individuals' expectations and their actual experiences. Gurr (1993) applied this theory to ethnic conflict, contending that group grievances can motivate individuals or groups to engage in violent action in response to their perceived relative deprivation. In his book "Minorities at Risk," Gurr explores the concept of relative deprivation and its link to minority groups at risk for ethno-political conflict. He argues that disparities between various groups in society can heighten the sense of relative deprivation experienced by minority groups, increasing the likelihood of violent action. Gurr highlights that the sense of relative deprivation is particularly acute when the gap between minority and majority groups is significant and enduring and when minorities feel unjustly treated by the majority (Gurr, 1993). Cederman et al. (2010) have employed the relative deprivation theory to expound upon the importance of group grievances in ethnic conflict. They argue that group-level disparities in resources and opportunities can be significant contributors to the initiation of armed conflict. Meanwhile, Mansfield and Snyder (1995) have used the same theory to explore why some ethnic groups opt for violent means while others do not. Their research suggests that groups experiencing greater political exclusion and economic deprivation are more likely to resort to violence (Mansfield & Snyder, 1995). Gurr's work underscores the need to address the underlying grievances that fuel conflicts. However, the relative deprivation theory has not been immune to critique from other scholars. Smith et al. (2012) have raised concerns about the reliability and validity of measures of relative deprivation, as they may not always capture the intricate and subjective nature of people's sense of disadvantage. Similarly, Berezin (2012) posits that this theory may not always account for why certain individuals or groups partake in collective action or social movements, as people may have other motivations or may not perceive themselves as deprived. Finally, Gamson (1992) has argued that the theory overlooks the role of cultural and social factors in shaping collective action and that these factors can be just as crucial as economic or material factors.

In summary, the relative deprivation theory has been a valuable framework for understanding the role of group grievances in ethnic conflict. The theory highlights the importance of addressing underlying grievances to prevent violent conflict.

BACKGROUND OF THE BOKO HARAM CONFLICT

According to Shuaibu et al (2015), Boko Haram emerged in Nigeria in 2002 as an extremist Islamic group founded by Mohammed Yusuf, a Borno State cleric. The group's name in the Hausa language means "Western education is forbidden." The International Crisis Group (2012) observes that Boko Haram targets marginalized and impoverished communities, particularly the Almajiris, who are Islamic students that beg for their upkeep, in the Northeastern region of Nigeria. Boko Haram primarily operates in Borno, Yobe, and Adamawa states in the Northeastern region of Nigeria (International Crisis Group, 2014). Initially, Boko Haram operated as a peaceful Islamic organization that provided religious education and social services to the poor, advocating for an Islamic state governed by Sharia law free from Western influence. However, following the death of Yusuf in police custody in 2009, the group became increasingly radicalized and began attacking the government, churches, and schools in

the region. His death sparked widespread violence and unrest in northeastern Nigeria, with Boko Haram launching retaliatory attacks against the government and civilians (Shuaibu et al, 2015). These attacks were also targeted at Christians who the group perceived to extol the values they stand for such as religion, western civilization and democracy, hence, making the expression of political grievances adopt a religious character (Ike, 2022).

Abubakar Shekau took over the leadership of Boko Haram following Yusuf's extrajudicial killing by the Nigerian military, and he transformed the group into a more lethal and sophisticated organization. Under Shekau's leadership, Boko Haram executed a series of high-profile attacks on government and civilian targets, including the 2011 bombing of the United Nations building in Abuja (Thurston, 2018) and the 2014 abduction of over 200 schoolgirls in Chibok (Ugwueze & Onuoha, 2020). According to the 2022 Global Terrorism Index report by the Institute for Economics and Peace (IEP, 2022), Boko Haram caused 7,401 fatalities in Nigeria and 1,224 in Cameroon between 2007 and 2021. The report also indicates that the Islamic State in West Africa (ISWA), which originated from Boko Haram, caused 954 fatalities in Sub-Saharan Africa during the same period (IEP, 2022). These attacks have had severe consequences, including significant loss of life, displacement of millions of people (Council on Foreign Relations, 2018), and grave economic repercussions in the region. Boko Haram's recruitment strategy targets vulnerable and marginalized populations, particularly the Almajiris who are Islamic students that beg for their upkeep, and its violent tactics make it a significant threat to regional stability and human security in Nigeria and beyond (Aghedo and Osumah, 2012). The group promises its members a better life in an Islamic state governed by Sharia law free from Western influence. Boko Haram's violent insurgency has had a devastating impact on the security and stability of Nigeria and the wider West African region, making it one of the world's deadliest terrorist organizations. The Institute for Economics and Peace (IEP, 2020) ranks Boko Haram among the three deadliest terrorist groups globally. Currently, Nigeria ranks eight on the Global Terrorism Index (IEP, 2023). Despite various measures implemented by the Nigerian government, civil society groups, and the international community, including military operations, negotiations, de-radicalization and re-integration programs, Boko Haram remains a formidable threat. Programs such as the proposed re-integration of former terrorists has been noted to be devoid of community input in design, and as such fueled resentment towards its implementation (Ike et al, 2020). These government efforts have largely been ineffective, and the group continues to pose a significant challenge to regional security and stability (Council on Foreign Relations, 2018).

CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF THE FRUSTRATION AGGRESSION THEORY AS A DRIVER OF THE BOKO HARAM CONFLICT.

In the context of the Boko Haram conflict, the frustration-aggression theory proposes that when individuals are unable to achieve their goals or experience positive outcomes, they may feel frustrated, which can lead to aggressive behavior (Apter, 1992; Felson & Tedeschi, 1993). Bandura (1973) suggests that aggression can be a natural response to frustration, which can be directed towards the source of the frustration or displaced onto other targets. Economic, political, and social frustration are three key aspects that contribute to the aggression of Boko Haram toward the Nigerian government and civilians (Akinyetun, 2020).

Economic frustration is a crucial factor that leads to aggression as it can cause feelings of hopelessness and despair, which can fuel support for extremist groups like Boko Haram. The northeastern region of Nigeria, where Boko Haram is based, is among the poorest areas in the country, with high levels of unemployment and limited economic opportunities (Akinyetun, 2020). Poverty in Nigeria can be categorized into four dimensions, namely health, education, living standards, and work and shocks, according to the Nigeria Multidimensional Poverty Index report by the National Bureau of Statistics (2022). The Nigeria Poverty Map (2023) further reveals that approximately 63% (133 million) of the total population in Nigeria are multidimensionally poor, with 65% (86.1 million) residing in the northern part of the country. Additionally, 75% (2,250,000) of the population of Borno state, the birthplace, and stronghold of Boko Haram, are multidimensionally poor, with living standards deprivation being a significant factor contributing to poverty, according to the National Bureau of Statistics (2023). Moreover, 34.3% and 53% of the people living in Borno state suffer from food insecurity and lack of housing materials, respectively, as indicated by the Nigeria Poverty Map (2023). Boko Haram has exploited economic frustration by providing food, medical care, and education to impoverished communities in the region, winning the loyalty of some residents who feel neglected by the government (Akinyetun, 2020). By positioning itself as a provider of social services, the group has used economic frustration to recruit and retain supporters. Boko Haram's aggression towards the government can be seen as a response to political frustration. The group aims to establish an Islamic state in Nigeria and has carried out violent attacks against the government and other symbols of authority (Akinyetun, 2020). Boko Haram leaders have expressed frustration with the government's response to their demands and used violence to try to force the government to negotiate with them (Akinyetun, 2020). By attacking government officials, buildings, police, and military targets, the group seeks to exert control over the political system and advance its agenda. Social frustration has also played a significant role in the Boko Haram conflict. Nigeria is a diverse country with multiple ethnic and religious groups, and tensions between these groups have fueled violence and conflict in the past. Boko Haram has exploited these social tensions by framing its fight as a struggle between Muslims and non-Muslims, attacking Christian churches and communities, as well as other groups that it perceives as opposed to its goals (Okeke-Uzodike and Onapajo, 2015). The group's aggression towards these groups can be seen as a response to social frustration, as it seeks to assert the dominance of its own religious and cultural identity.

To address the root causes of conflict and promote peaceful solutions, the Nigerian government needs to understand the underlying causes of frustration (Okeke-Uzodike and Onapajo, 2015). The frustration-aggression theory provides a useful framework for understanding the drivers of the Boko Haram conflict (Onuoha, 2012).

CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF RELATIVE DEPRIVATION THEORY AS A DRIVER OF THE BOKO HARAM CONFLICT.

Boko Haram is believed to have been fueled by a sense of relative deprivation, particularly among those living in the northeastern region, which is one of the poorest and most marginalized parts of the country (Gerges, 2018). Due to the region's limited access to essential amenities like education, healthcare, and access to clean water, many people feel neglected by the central government. Boko Haram has capitalized on this frustration by offering an alternative vision of society based on Islamic

law and promising to provide social services and economic opportunities to its supporters while challenging the corruption and inequality of the Nigerian state. In response to the Boko Haram insurgency, the Nigerian government launched the Presidential Initiative for the North East (PINE) in 2012 to promote economic development in the region. However, the initiative's implementation has been slow, and the impact has not been felt by the people of the region. The lack of economic development in the northeastern region of Nigeria has created a sense of relative deprivation, which the group has been able to leverage to recruit members and carry out attacks against the government and the people of the region. According to Akinyetun, (2020), Boko Haram's ideology is rooted in a sense of relative deprivation among its members and supporters, who perceive themselves as being oppressed and marginalized by the Nigerian state and society. Therefore, the emergence of Boko Haram can be seen as a response to the perceived relative deprivation of northeastern Nigeria compared to other parts of the country. Boko Haram's promise to provide social services and economic opportunities to its supporters can be seen as an attempt to address the perceived gap between what its members and supporters believe they are entitled to and what they receive compared to others in Nigerian society, as described by the relative deprivation theory. Boko Haram has even established a "shadow government" in northeastern Nigeria, providing basic services such as schools and healthcare facilities to communities that have been neglected by the Nigerian state.

THE ROLE OF THE NIGERIAN GOVERNMENT IN FUELING THE CONFLICT.

The ideology of Boko Haram, a violent extremist group in Nigeria, is based on Salafist jihadism, which advocates the use of force to achieve its objectives (Olofinbiyi and Singh, 2020). The group's adoption of this ideology was influenced by several factors, including the killing and arrest of its members by the Nigerian Army in 2009, resulting in the loss of key leadership figures (Ibrahim, 2017). The absence of accountability within the army for the actions of its personnel also contributed to the group's radicalization (Okeke-Uzodike and Onapajo, 2015). Furthermore, Mohammed Yusuf, the group's founder, was influenced by the violence perpetrated against his followers, leading him to promote violence as a means of achieving their objectives (Ibrahim, 2017). Consequently, the group's tactics shifted towards an increased reliance on violent means to achieve their goals. As Yusuf stated in a 2009 interview, the group considered anyone who opposed them as an enemy and would deal with them accordingly (David et al, 2015). The adoption of the Salafist jihadist ideology by Boko Haram and its increasing use of violence led to a significant rise in the number of attacks carried out by the group, causing a high number of casualties (Vision of Humanity, 2022). The tactics employed by the group have been widely condemned by governments and human rights organizations (Human Rights Watch, 2012). The Nigerian Army's actions in arresting and killing members of the group, particularly the extrajudicial killing of Yusuf, combined with its lack of accountability, played a significant role in the group's radicalization and embrace of violent tactics. Additionally, the group's adherence to the Salafist jihadist ideology has been a driving force behind its violent activities (Thurston, 2018), as well as the government's harsh treatment of the group.

The emergence of Boko Haram as a severe security threat to Nigeria is significantly attributed to the inadequate response of the Nigerian government during its early stages. In 2009, the government enacted a law requiring motorcyclists to wear helmets to prevent fatalities and injuries from road accidents. However, Boko Haram perceived the law as a challenge to its anti-Western education and

influence ideology and began attacking motorcyclists and burning their bikes in protest (Abubakar, 2017). This provoked clashes between the group and the Nigerian police, who were responsible for enforcing the law (Onuoha, 2012). The conflict escalated as the police arrested and detained Boko Haram members, leading to increased resentment and retaliation by the group (David et al, 2015). As correctly noted by Ike et al. (2022), the Nigerian government's tendency to use force as a response to most issues, as evident in its handling of the End SARS protest of October 2020, was also evident in its initial approach to the Boko Haram crisis. The Nigerian government's failure to adequately address the conflict over the helmet law was a significant factor in the group's radicalization and increasing use of violence. This underscores the importance of a comprehensive approach to addressing security threats that addresses the root causes of the problem. The government must prioritize effective and strategic measures aimed at resolving the Boko Haram crisis and ensuring the safety and security of its citizens. The response of Nigerian security agencies, particularly the police, in addressing the Boko Haram conflict has been a contentious issue. Scholars have argued that the police's excessive use of force has contributed to the radicalization of the group and its recruitment efforts (Dowd, 2015). Their actions have created a sense of marginalization and injustice among local communities, which the group has exploited to its advantage. Furthermore, the police's human rights violations, including extrajudicial killings, torture, and arbitrary detention, have further fueled the conflict (Human Rights Watch, 2012). Amnesty International's (2015) report accused the Nigerian security forces of perpetrating extrajudicial killings, torture, and other abuses against suspected Boko Haram members, which only served to worsen the violence. In retaliation to the Boko Haram attacks, the government sent a large contingent of soldiers and heavy weaponry to Maiduguri, resulting in the death of Boko Haram members. However, this military intervention exacerbated local populations' alienation and weakened trust in the government, making it easier for Boko Haram to recruit new members. Scholars suggest that the government could have avoided this outcome by pursuing dialogue with the group instead of relying on force (Agbiboa, 2013). Scholars also propose that bringing Yusuf to trial, instead of killing him, could have led to a more peaceful resolution of the conflict (Ibrahim, 2017). However, Yusuf's killing was a pivotal moment in the conflict, contributing to the radicalization and expansion of Boko Haram (Agbiboa, 2013). The government's use of military force in response to the group's attacks has also been criticized for its significant toll on civilians and human rights violations, and for fueling resentment among Yusuf's followers, who interpreted it as evidence of government oppression and brutality.

The Nigerian government's efforts to combat Boko Haram have come under criticism due to several factors, according to scholars. One issue is the government's crackdown on almajiris, which are Islamic schools. The government's decision to shut down these schools as part of its anti-Boko Haram efforts has been condemned for limiting access to education and leading to the radicalization of some students (International Crisis Group, 2014). Some children who have been forced out of almajiris schools have reportedly joined Boko Haram, either because of indoctrination or due to a lack of other options. Additionally, the government's response to the 2014 Chibok girls' kidnapping has been criticized for being insufficient and slow, resulting in a loss of confidence in its ability to address security threats posed by Boko Haram (Adeyanju, 2014). Another contributing factor to the conflict is the alleged political manipulation of the group by some Nigerian politicians. According to David et al (2015), some politicians have used Boko Haram for their political interests. For instance, Governor Ali Modu Sheriff of Borno State has been accused of being involved in the emergence of the group, using

it to secure political power, and later abandoning its cause, which caused some members to become disillusioned and intensify their violent activities (International Crisis group, 2014). Some sources also alleged that Sheriff provided financial and material support to the group during his tenure as governor and had links to the group, which he allegedly used to consolidate his political power (Olaniyan, 2015). Similarly, Senator Ali Ndume of Borno State has also being linked to the preservation of the Boko Haram Terrorist group (Adibe, 2013). Furthermore, the use of the Civilian Joint Task Force (CJTF) by the Nigerian government has raised concerns about human rights abuses and intercommunal tensions. Omenma and Hendricks (2018) report that the CJTF's reliance on extrajudicial measures has intensified conflict in the region. Similarly, Amnesty International (2013) has accused the CJTF of engaging in activities such as torture, arbitrary detention, and extrajudicial killings, which have contributed to the escalation of violence and eroded trust between local communities and the government. Overall, the government's delayed response to the group's grievances and its heavy-handed tactics have worsened the situation. The government's military approach has resulted in numerous human rights cases of abuse, including extrajudicial killings and torture, which have only fueled resentment and made it easier for Boko Haram to recruit new members (Dowd, 2015; Human Rights Watch, 2012). A diplomatic dialogue could have been a more productive approach, as it could have addressed the underlying grievances that led to the group's emergence in the first place (Agbibo, 2013; Ibrahim, 2017).

To sum up, the involvement of the Nigerian government in the Boko Haram conflict has been significant, marked by various acts and omissions. These include the extrajudicial execution of Mohammed Yusuf and the use of military force in retaliation to the group's offensives among other actions. These measures have contributed to the radicalization and growth of Boko Haram, which, in turn, has eroded trust in the government among local communities. Had the government pursued negotiations with the group, instead of solely relying on military intervention, a more peaceful resolution of the conflict would have been attainable.

REFERENCES:

Abubakar, D. (2017). 'From Sectarianism to Terrorism in Northern Nigeria: A Closer Look at Boko Haram.' In: Varin, C., Abubakar, D. (eds) *Violent Non-State Actors in Africa*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. Available at: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-51352-2_2 [Accessed: 1 March 2023]

Adeyanju, A. (2014) "A Textual Analysis of Online Newspapers Readers' Comments on the Coverage of Chibok School Girls Kidnap", *Covenant Journal of Communication*, 2(2). Available at: <https://journals.covenantuniversity.edu.ng/index.php/cjoc/article/view/211> [Accessed: 1 May 2023].

Adibe, J. (2013). 'What do we really know about Boko Haram. Boko Haram: Anatomy of a Crisis.' Bristol, UK: *e-International Relations*, pp.9-15. Available at: <https://www.e-ir.info/2012/11/14/what-do-we-really-know-about-boko-haram/> [Accessed 15th March 2023].

Agbibo, D. E. (2013). 'Why Boko Haram Exists: The Relative Deprivation Perspective.' *African Conflict and Peacebuilding Review*, 3(1), 144–157. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2979/africanconfpeacrevi.3.1.144>

Agbibo, D.E. (2013). 'The Ongoing Campaign of Terror in Nigeria: Boko Haram versus the State.' *Stability International Journal of Security and Development*, 2(3), p.Art. 52. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5334/sta.cl>

- Aghedo, I. and Osumah, O., 2014. 'Bread, Not Bullets: Boko Haram And Insecurity Management In Northern Nigeria.' *African Study Monographs*, 35(3/4), pp.205-229. <http://dx.doi.org/10.14989/193251>
- Akinyetun, T.S. (2020) 'A Theoretical Assessment of Boko Haram Insurgency in Nigeria from Relative Deprivation and Frustration-Aggression Perspectives', *African Journal of Terrorism and Insurgency Research [AJOTIR]*, 1(2), 87+, Available: <https://link.gale.com/apps/doc/A666351085/AONE?u=anon~6f42d5fb&sid=googleScholar&xid=7c022857> [Accessed 12 March 2023].
- Amnesty International, (2013). Nigeria: Trapped in the cycle of violence. Available at: <https://www.amnesty.org/en/documents/afr44/027/2013/en/> [Accessed 14th March 2023].
- Amnesty International. (2015). Nigeria: Stars on their shoulders. Blood on their hands. War crimes committed by the Nigerian military. Available at: <https://www.amnesty.org/download/Documents/AFR4432362015ENGLISH.PDF> [Accessed: 14th March 2023]
- Apter, M. J. (1992). *The dangerous edge: The psychology of excitement*. Simon and Schuster.
- Bandura, A. (1973). *Aggression: A social learning analysis*. Prentice-Hall.
- Berezin, M. (2002). 'Secure States: Towards a Political Sociology of Emotion.' *The Sociological Review*, 50(2_suppl), 33–52. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1467-954X.2002.tb03590.x>
- Berkowitz, L. (1962). *Aggression: A social psychological analysis*. McGraw-Hill. Available at: <https://psycnet.apa.org/record/1963-06518-000> [Accessed: 17th March 2023]
- Berkowitz, L. (1989). 'Frustration-aggression hypothesis: Examination and reformulation.' *Psychological Bulletin*, 106(1), 59–73. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.106.1.59>
- Bushman, B. J., Baumeister, R. F., & Phillips, C. M. (2001). 'Do people aggress to improve their mood? Catharsis beliefs, affect regulation opportunity, and aggressive responding.' *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 81(1), 17–32. Available at: <http://www-personal.umich.edu/~bbushman/bbp01.pdf> [Accessed: 22nd March 2023]
- Cederman, L.-E., Wimmer, A., & Min, B. (2010). 'Why do ethnic groups rebel?: New data and analysis.' *World Politics*, 62(1), 87-119. DOI: <https://www.jstor.org/stable/40646192>
- Council on Foreign Relations. (2018). Nigeria's Battle With Boko Haram. Available at: <https://www.cfr.org/backgrounder/nigerias-battle-boko-haram> [Accessed: 22nd April 2023]
- David, O.J., Asuelime, L.E., Onapajo, H. (2015). 'Evolution, Ideological Foundation, and Strategy of Boko Haram Terrorism in Nigeria. In: Boko Haram.' *Springer Briefs in Political Science*. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-21230-2_4
- Dollard, J., Miller, N. E., Doob, L. W., Mowrer, O. H., & Sears, R. R. (1939). 'Frustration and Aggression.' *Yale University Press*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1037/10022-000>
- Dowd, C. (2015) "Grievances, governance and Islamist violence in sub-Saharan Africa," *The Journal of Modern African Studies*. Cambridge University Press, 53(4), pp. 505–531. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0022278X15000737>
- Felson, R. B., & Tedeschi, J. T. (1993). 'Aggression and violence: Social interactionist perspectives.' (Eds.) *American Psychological Association*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1037/10123-000>
- Gamson, W. A. (1992). *The social psychology of collective action*. In *Frontiers in social movement theory* (pp. 53-76). Yale University Press.
- Gupta, D.K. (2020). 'Understanding Terrorism and Political Violence: The Life Cycle of Birth, Growth, Transformation, and Demise' (2nd ed.). *Routledge*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780429297427>
- Gurr, T. R. (1970). *Why men rebel*. Princeton University Press.
- Gurr, T. R. (1993). *Minorities at risk: A global view of ethno-political conflicts*. United States Institute of Peace Press.
- Gurr, T. R. (2000). *Peoples versus states: Minorities at risk in the new century*. United States Institute of Peace Press.

- Horgan, J. G. (2017). 'Psychology of terrorism: Introduction to the special issue.' *American Psychologist*, 72(3), 199–204. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1037/amp0000148>
- Human Rights Watch. (2012). Spiraling violence: Boko Haram attacks and security force abuses in Nigeria. Available at: <https://www.hrw.org/report/2012/10/11/spiraling-violence/boko-haram-attacks-and-security-force-abuses-nigeria> [Accessed: 22nd March 2023]
- Ibrahim, I. (2017), "The Wave of Jihadist Insurgency in West Africa: Global Ideology, Local Context, Individual Motivations", *West African Papers*, No. 7, OECD Publishing, Paris, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1787/eb95c0a9-en>
- Ike, T.J. 2022, "'Its' like being a Christian is tantamount to Victimisation: A Qualitative study of Christian experiences and perceptions of insecurity and terrorism in Nigeria", *Cogent Social Sciences*, Vol. 8, No. 1. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/23311886.2022.2071032>
- Ike, T.J., Singh D., Jidong, D. E., Murphy, S. & Ayobi, E.E., (2021) 'Rethinking reintegration in Nigeria: community perceptions of former Boko Haram combatants' *Third World Quarterly*, 42:4, 661-678, DOI: <https://doi-org.ezproxy.tees.ac.uk/10.1080/01436597.2021.1872376>
- Ike, T.J., Singh, D., Jidong, D.E., Ike, L.M. & Ayobi, E.E. (2022), "Public perspectives of interventions aimed at building confidence in the Nigerian police: A systematic review", *Journal of Policing, Intelligence and Counter Terrorism*, Vol. 17, No. 1, pp. 95-116. DOI: <https://doi-org.ezproxy.tees.ac.uk/10.1080/18335330.2021.1892167>
- Institute for Economics and Peace (IEP), (2020). Global terrorism index 2020: Measuring the impact of terrorism. Available at: <https://www.economicsandpeace.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/11/GTI-2020-web-2.pdf> [Accessed: 24th March 2023]
- Institute for Economics and Peace (IEP), (2022). Global terrorism index 2022: Measuring the impact of terrorism. Available at: <https://www.economicsandpeace.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/GTI-2022-web-09062022.pdf> [Accessed: 24th March 2023]
- Institute for Economics and Peace (IEP), (2023). Global terrorism index 2023: Measuring the impact of terrorism. Available at: <https://www.economicsandpeace.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/03/GTI-2023-web-170423.pdf> [Accessed: 28th April 2023]
- International Crisis Group. (2012). Curbing violence in Nigeria (I): The Jos crisis. Available at: <https://www.crisisgroup.org/africa/west-africa/nigeria/curbing-violence-nigeria-i-jos-crisis> [Accessed: 24th March 2023]
- International Crisis Group. (2014). Curbing Violence in Nigeria (II): The Boko Haram Insurgency. Available at: <https://www.crisisgroup.org/africa/west-africa/nigeria/curbing-violence-nigeria-ii-boko-haram-insurgency> [Accessed: 24th March 2023]
- Levy, M. A., & Thompson, W. R. (2010). Causes of war. John Wiley & Sons. Available at: <http://slantchev.ucsd.edu/courses/ps143a/readings/Levy%20%20Thompson%20-%20Causes%20of%20War.pdf> [Accessed: 2nd April 2023]
- Mansfield, E. D., & Snyder, J. (1995). 'Democratization and the Danger of War'. *International Security*, 20(1), 5–38. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.2307/2539213>
- Marcus-Newhall, A., Pedersen, W. C., Carlson, M., & Miller, N. (2000). 'Displaced aggression is alive and well: A meta-analytic review.' *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 78(4), 670–689. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-3514.78.4.670>
- National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). (2022). Nigeria Multidimensional Poverty Index Report. Abuja: National Bureau of Statistics.
- National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). (2023). Nigeria Poverty Map. Abuja: National Bureau of Statistics.
- Nigeria Poverty Map, (2023). How do different Dimensions contribute to poverty in Nigeria? Available at: <https://www.nigeriapoveritymap.com/dimensions> [Accessed 28th March 2023]
- Okeke-Uzodike, U. and Onapajo, H., 2015. The rage of insurgency: Why Boko Haram may remain untamed. *African Renaissance*, 12(2), pp.49-70. Available at: <https://hdl.handle.net/10520/EJC174534> [Accessed: 2nd April 2023]
- Olaniyan, O.D., (2015). 'Effect of Boko Haram insurgency on the Nigerian education system.' *Journal of Research*, 24(2), pp.1-9. Available at: <https://globalacademicgroup.com/journals/nard/EFFECT%20OF%20BOKO%20HARAM%20INSURGENCY%20ON%20THE%20NIGERIAN%20EDUCATION%20SYSTEM-%20.%20D.%20Olaniyan.pdf> [Accessed 15th March 2023].

- Olofinbiyi, S.A. And Singh, S.B., (2020), 'On the Crisis of Boko Haram Terrorism: An Interactive Theoretical Approach', *African Journal of Peace and Conflict Studies*. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.31920/2634-3665/2020/s9n2a1>
- Omenma, J. & Hendricks, C. (2018). 'Counterterrorism in Africa: an analysis of the civilian joint task force and military partnership in Nigeria.' *Security Journal*. Available at: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.1057/s41284-018-0131-8> [Accessed 26th March, 2023]
- Onuoha, F. (2012) 'The audacity of the Boko Haram: Background, analysis and emerging trend.' *Secur J* 25, 134–151. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1057/sj.2011.15>
- Shuaibu, S.S., Salleh, M.A. and Shehu, A.Y., (2015). 'The impact of Boko Haram insurgency on Nigerian national security.' *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 5(6), pp.254-266. DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.6007/IJARBS/v5-i6/1676>
- Smith, H. J., Pettigrew, T. F., Pippin, G. M., & Bialosiewicz, S. (2012). 'R'elative Deprivation: A Theoretical and Meta-Analytic Review.' *Personality and Social Psychology Review*, 16(3), 203–232. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1177/1088868311430825>
- Thurston, A. (2018), *Boko Haram: The History of an African Jihadist Movement*. Princeton: Princeton University Press. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1515/9781400888481> [Accessed 17th March 2023]
- Ugwueze, M. & Onuoha, F. C. (2020) 'Hard Versus Soft Measures to Security: Explaining the Failure of Counter-Terrorism Strategy in Nigeria,' *Journal of Applied Security Research*, 15:4, 547-567, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/19361610.2020.1811936>
- Vision of Humanity, (2022). 2022 Global Terrorism Index: Overall Terrorism Index Score. Available at: <http://visionofhumanity.org/indexes/global-terrorism-index/> [Accessed: 24th March 2023]
- Yusuf, S. (2017). Presidential initiative for the northeast (PINE): An overview. United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs.